

PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTION WITH SOME INORGANIC COLLOIDS AS ACTIVE AGENTS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF LIGHT IN VARIOUS STATES OF POLARISATION. PART XII. THE PHOTOCHEMICAL OXIDATION OF GLUCOSE AND LAEVULOSE BY METHYLENE BLUE WITH FERRIC HYDROXIDE SOL AS THE PHOTO-SENSITISER.

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Preparation of Ferric Hydroxide Sol.

The sol was prepared after Dumansky (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 34, 1067). A dilute solution of Merck's 'extra pure' ferric chloride was treated with Merck's extra pure ammonium carbonate in the cold until the precipitate formed just dissolved. The deep red coloured sol thus formed was filtered and then subjected to hot dialysis at 70°-80° for 12 days.

Estimation of Ferric Hydroxide Sol.

The ferric hydroxide sol was gravimetrically estimated as Fe_2O_3 (Treadwell, 1924 Ed., p. 94). The sol was also iodometrically estimated by Carl Mohr's method (*Ann. Chem. Pharm.*, 105, 53). The results obtained by the two methods were found to be identical.

Spectrophotometric readings were taken with the quartz cell filled with water or mixtures of different concentrations of methylene blue and ferric hydroxide sol in the red region of the spectrophotometer (632 μ) where the absorption due to the sol was the smallest. A graph (Fig. 1) was obtained

by plotting $\log \tan \theta_2 - \log \tan \theta_1$ against the concentrations of methylene blue at a particular sol concentration. A separate graph was traced with each concentration of the sol (*cf.* Part XIII).

A solution of methylene blue or methylene blue and glucose or methylene blue and ferric hydroxide remained unaffected when exposed to the radiation of wave-length $366\mu\mu$ and $254\mu\mu$. A mixture of glucose, ferric hydroxide sol and methylene blue does not react when kept in the dark for 24 hours.

R E S U L T S .

A very long induction period (from 6 hours to 14 hours depending upon the intensity of exciting light) was observed in the photochemical reaction even when the air in the reaction mixture was removed by passing nitrogen through it. In the following experiments, the induction period was considerably minimised (from 6 hours to less than 2 hours) by pre-exposing the reaction mixture to sunlight for 5 minutes.

TABLE I.

Reaction mixture not pre-exposed to sun-light. d (thickness of the reaction cell) = 0.5 cm. Composition of reaction mixture:—Sol (as Fe_2O_3) = 0.0107M; glucose = 1%; methylene blue = 50×10^{-6} M. $p_x = 4.8$. Temp. = 29°. * I_{abs} = 2352.

Time.	Spectrophotometric reading. (θ_2)	Zero reading. (θ_1)	Conc. of methylene blue $\times 10^6$.	K_0 (no. of mols transformed per c.c. per sec.) $\times 10^{12}$.
(1) 0 hr.	74.5	51.5		
(2) 6	66.5	"		
(3) 6½	63.5		22.0	
(4) 7	60.5	"	15.6	3.56 (from 3 & 4)
(5) 7½	57.0	"	9.5	3.38 (from 4 & 5)
				<u>Mean—3.37</u>

The reaction is zero-molecular with respect to methylene blue.

* I_{abs} , here and in the following tables denotes the intensity of radiation absorbed by the reaction mixture in ergs per sq. cm. per sec.

Effect of Varying the Concentration of Reductant.

TABLE II.

Temp. = 29°. Sol = 0.0107M. Methylene blue = $50 \times 10^{-6}M$.
 $p_{\pi} = 4.8$. I_{abs} at 254 $\mu\mu = 1380$ and at 366 $\mu\mu = 2160$. $d = 0.5$ cm.
 γ = quantum efficiency.

Conc. of reductant. Glucose.	$K \times 10^{12}$ at 254 $\mu\mu$.	γ at 254 $\mu\mu$.	$K \times 10^{12}$ at 366 $\mu\mu$.	γ at 366 $\mu\mu$.
8%	—	—	3.80	0.00282
4	1.48	0.00252	3.80	0.00282
2	1.49	0.00263	3.78	0.00282
1	1.33	0.00226	3.02	0.00225
0.5	1.075	0.00183	2.53	0.00189
0.25	0.767	0.00130	1.65	0.00125
Laevulose 1%	...	...	10.00	0.0075
0.5	4.48	0.0094	9.93	0.0075
0.25	4.48	0.0094	9.93	0.0075
0.125	3.92	0.0066	9.38	0.0070
0.0625	3.05	0.0052	8.30	0.0062
0.0313	2.45	0.0042	6.82	0.0051

From the above table it will be found that upto a certain concentration of the reductant, the velocity constant does not undergo any change with change in concentration of the reductant. Below this limiting concentration of the reductant, the velocity constant diminishes with the decrease in the concentration of reductant and $1/K$ plotted against $1/C$ gives a straight line (Figs. 2 and 3).

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

Effect of Varying the Concentration of Sol.

TABLE III.

Temp. = 29°. Methylene blue = $50 \times 10^{-6} M$.

Wave-length.	Conc. of sol.	Reductant.	p_H .	I_{abs} .	$K \times 10^{12}$.
Glucose.					
254 $\mu\mu$	0.0107 M	1%	4.80	1366	1.365
"	0.0054	"	4.86	1352	1.275
366 $\mu\mu$	0.0107	"	4.80	2496	3.497
"	0.0054	"	4.86	2482	3.242
Laevulose.					
254 $\mu\mu$	0.0107	0.25%	4.80	1366	4.47
"	0.0054	"	4.86	1352	4.15
366 $\mu\mu$	0.0107	"	4.80	2163	10.08
"	0.0054	"	4.86	2158	9.67
"	0.0017	"	4.95	2145	9.35

From the above table it is evident that the velocity constant diminishes slightly with diminishing concentration of the sol, the intensity of radiation absorbed by the sol also diminishing slightly.

Effect of Varying the p_H of the Reacting System.

TABLE IV.

Temp. = 29°. Sol = 0.0107 M. Methylene blue = $50.0 \times 10^{-6} M$.

I_{abs} at 254 $\mu\mu$ = 1380 and at 366 $\mu\mu$ = 2544 with glucose, and at 366 $\mu\mu$ = 2032 with laevulose.

p_H .	Reductant. Glucose.	$K \times 10^{12}$ at 254 $\mu\mu$.	γ at 254 $\mu\mu$.	$K \times 10^{12}$ at 366 $\mu\mu$.	γ at 366 $\mu\mu$.
5.5	1%	1.00	0.00166	2.00	0.00014
5.1	"	1.17	0.00198	2.69	0.00166
4.8	"	1.33	0.00228	3.55	0.00223
4.5	"	0.99	0.00166	...	...
4.3	"	...	...	1.68	0.00100
4.0	"	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Laevulose.					
5.5	0.25%	3.1	0.0052	6.30	0.0050
5.1	"	...	...	7.47	0.0069
4.8	"	4.48	0.0092	9.33	0.0074
4.3	"	2.70	0.0045	4.20	0.0033
4.0	"	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

From the above table it is evident that the velocity constant passes through a maximum to almost zero as the p_n of the system decreases. The maximum velocity constant is obtained at p_n 4.8.

Effect of Varying the Intensity of Absorbed Radiation.

The intensity of radiation (366 $\mu\mu$) absorbed by the reaction mixture was measured by noting the deflections of a Moll galvanometer connected with a Moll thermopile placed behind the reaction cell, first with the cell filled with pure water and then with the reaction mixture. The difference gave the light absorbed by the reaction mixture (*vide* Part I).

The energy of total incident radiation of 254 $\mu\mu$ was similarly measured with a Moll thermopile and a Moll galvanometer. The galvanometer deflections were noted with the cell, first filled with pure water and then with normal potassium nitrite solution which absorbed completely the extreme ultraviolet radiation (254 $\mu\mu$). The difference gave the intensity of total ultraviolet radiation (254 $\mu\mu$).

The amount of light absorbed by ferric hydroxide sol alone was calculated by the approximate extinction formula for mixtures. I_{abs} by ferric hydroxide sol (A).

$$= I_{incident} \left(I - e^{-\epsilon_1^\lambda c_1 d_1 - \epsilon_2^\lambda c_2 d_2} \right) \times \frac{\epsilon_1^\lambda c_1}{\epsilon_1^\lambda c_1 + \epsilon_2^\lambda c_2} \quad \dots (A)$$

the extinction coefficients (at wave length λ) and concentrations of A and B (the other absorbing agent) being ϵ_1^λ , c_1 and ϵ_2^λ and c_2 respectively.

Molecular extinction coefficient of ferric hydroxide sol and methylene blue in the ultraviolet were measured by means of a Hilger quartz spectrograph in conjunction with a rotating sector. The values are given in Table V and Fig. 4.

FIG. 4.

TABLE V.

Absorbing substance.	Mol. extinct. coefficient at	
	254 $\mu\mu$.	366 $\mu\mu$.
Ferric hydroxide sol	10,747	5,373
Methylene blue	23,485	2,500

Effect of Varying the Intensity of Absorbed Radiation.

TABLE VI.

Temp. = 29^o. $p_n = 4.8$. $d = 0.5$ cm.

Wave-length.	Conc. of sol.	Reductant.	Conc. of Me blue. $\times 10^8$	I_{abs} (mix).	$K \times 10^{12}$.
Glucose.					
(a) 366 $\mu\mu$	0.0107M	1%	50.0M	2544	3.55
"	"	"	"	1681	2.39
Laevulose.					
(b) 366 $\mu\mu$	0.0107M	0.25%	50.0	2163	9.93
"	"	"	"	1542	7.48

The velocity constant varies directly as the intensity of radiation absorbed.

Quantum Efficiency of the Process.

As in Part XIII, the fraction of the radiation absorbed by the sol alone was taken into consideration while calculating the quantum efficiencies of these photochemical reactions and calculated by the equation (A).

In this case, the concentration of methylene blue being relatively very small and the molecular extinction coefficient of methylene blue and ferric hydroxide sol being of the same order, practically the whole of the absorbed light was absorbed by the sol. The quantum efficiency (γ) was much less than unity (*vide* Table II)

Temperature Coefficient of the Reaction.—The temperature coefficient is small being of the order of 1.1—1.2.

Influence of Polarised Light.

T A B L E VII.

Wave-length = 366 $\mu\mu$. Temp. = 29°. $p_x = 4.8$. Sol = 0.0107M.
Methylene blue = 50.0×10^{-6} M. Glucose = 1%.

Nature of light.	$I_{abs.}$	$K \times 10^{12}$.
(a) Ordinary	2492	3.48
(b) d-Circularly polarised (reaction mixture not pre-exposed to sunlight).	"	0.93
(c) l-Circularly polarised (reaction mixture not pre-exposed to sunlight).	"	1.02

In the last two cases (c and d) induction period was about 14 hours. Now from the above table we see that $V_l > V_o$, the terms having the usual significance.

D I S C U S S I O N .

Any mechanism of reaction that may be proposed should be in a position to explain the following facts:—

(1) The velocity of reaction with respect to methylene blue is zero-molecular.

(2) The reactions are attended with long induction periods.

(3) Upto a certain concentration of reductants, the velocity constant undergoes no change with change in concentration of reductant. Below this limiting concentration of reductants, the velocity constant diminishes with the decrease in the concentration of reductant and $1/C$ plotted against $1/K$ gives a straight line.

(4) The velocity constant diminishes slightly with diminishing concentration of sol, the intensity of absorbed radiation diminishing slightly.

(5) The constant passes through a maximum at $p_x = 4.8$ to almost zero as the p_x of the reacting system diminishes.

(6) The velocity constant varies directly as the intensity of absorbed radiation

(7) Temperature coefficient is small.

(8) The quantum efficiency which is very much less than unity, has almost the same value at 254 $\mu\mu$ and 366 $\mu\mu$.

The sol surface is completely covered with a unimolecular layer of the dye-molecule even at very low concentration of the dye. It is remarkable that the absorption of radiation by the dye-molecules directly does not lead to the photoreduction by reaction with reductant. But a dye-molecule can be brought into activated state by receiving energy from the elementary spaces of the ferric hydroxide sol surface which is also excited by the absorption of radiation.

The low quantum efficiency can be due to two reasons:—

- (a) Only a small fraction of the radiation absorbed by the sol is available for the activation of the dye-molecules on the surface of the sol or
 (b) the velocity of reaction between activated molecules and the reductant adsorbed on the surface of the sol is so slow that most of the former revert spontaneously to the normal state. It is difficult to decide between these two possibilities.

The velocity is given by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K' \cdot \frac{I}{N h \nu} \cdot C_s^a = K \quad \dots (i)$$

where C_s^a is the surface concentration of the reductant.

According to Langmuir

$$C_s^a = \frac{K_1 C_s^b}{K_2 + K_1 C_s^b} \quad \dots (ii)$$

where C_s^b is the concentration of reductant in solution.

When C_s^b is very large, $K_2 + K_1 C_s^b$ may be taken as equal to C_s^b

$$\text{or } \frac{dx}{dt} = K = \frac{K_1}{K_2} \quad \dots (iii)$$

That is, the velocity constant is independent of reductant concentration when the latter is high as has been experimentally found to be the case.

At a lower concentration of reductant K_2 can not be neglected in comparison to $K_1 C_s^b$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Hence } I/K &= K_2 \cdot \frac{K_2 + K_1 C_s^b}{K_1 C_s^b} \\ &= \frac{K_2}{C_s^b} + K_2 \quad \dots (vi) \end{aligned}$$

That is at low concentration of reductant, I/K plotted against, C_s^b should give a straight line. This has been experimentally realised.

The velocity of reaction has been found to be proportional to the intensity of absorbed radiation as is demanded by equation (i).